

RADIANT CREATOR Workshop “Bere Event”

11-12 July 2022, Orkney, Scotland

Hosted by:

- the University of Highlands and Islands; and,
- the James Hutton Institute

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Executive Summary

The aim of the workshop was for the RADIANT project to help showcase the bere barley value chain and engage with the range of stakeholders in this chain. This was achieved by inviting experts in bere both from industry and academia to engage with the range of research activities associated with bere barley and showcase best practices as well as success stories in the value chain. Time was also allowed for multiactors interactions through visits to some significant players in the bere value chain and tasting of some of the varying bere barley products.

The main outcomes of the workshop are as follows.

- Discussion between stakeholders of the bere value chain were constructive and productive, leading to new collaborations to help grow the value chain.
- The protocols for the deliberative choice experiments with farmers and for the choice experiments with consumers were tested for the first time, allowing the validation of the questionnaires, which will be used in future workshops in other EU countries, with adaptations related to the specific underutilised crop (UC) considered.
- Important qualitative issues related to the expansion of the supply chains of UCs were detected, including the trade-off between the benefits (including the price premium) of being a niche product related to a specific territory and the possibility to achieve crop and dietary diversification at a large scale.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and objectives

Bere (barley) is thought to be Britain's oldest cereal in continuous commercial cultivation. It was an important crop in the Highlands and Islands of Scotland, providing grain for milling and malting and straw for thatching, *etc.* However, the advent of higher-yielding barley varieties led to a sharp decline in bere cultivation during the 20th century.

Bere is a type of barley that over centuries of cultivation has become adapted to Scotland's climate, and low nutrient soils of marginal lands. The workshop showcased its heritage value, as a source of novel high-value Scottish products and genetic diversity for breeders to tackle issues of agricultural sustainability.

In Orkney, bere barley was saved from extinction around 30 years ago and is still used by Barony Mill which produces bere meal flour for local use in bere bannocks (bread) and the flour is distributed to farm shops across Scotland. While grain is used for producing Malt (Crafty Maltsters, Crisp Malt, Bairds); Whisky (Bruichladdich, Raasay, Scapa) and Beer (Arbikie, Swannay). DVC that represents the use of UCs for food and drinks. Bere is also grown on the Outer Hebrides (part of Scotland's Western Isles) as part of a cereal landrace mixture used for animal feed.

The importance of a dynamic value chain for underutilised crops (UC) was showcased through visits to:

- a field trial of bere demonstrating its unique abilities to cope with marginal soils;
- a mill producing beremeal (bere flour) for local use in bere bannocks (bread) and the flour is distributed to specialist outlets across Scotland; and,
- a local brewery brewing beer with Orkney grown bere barley.

Interacting with stakeholders was a key element during the bere Showcase: heritage, sustainability, and commercialisation session with participants able to visits stalls, listen to spotlight presentations, and taste the diverse range of bere-based products. There was also an in-depth discussion among the wide range of delegates, that provided unique insight and learning regarding the opportunities and challenges in facilitating greater cultivation and consumption of this specific underutilised crop.

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

The CREATOR BERE workshop took place over two days in Orkney in Scotland. The event was held in English and was attended by 53 stakeholders, 7 of whom joined remotely.

Different stakeholder groups were represented at the event (Figure 1). Most participants were either academics or researchers (55 %) followed by processors (21 %) and growers (14 %).

Figure 1. Distribution of the participants by stakeholder groups: Academics/Researchers – 28; Growers - 7; Processors – 11; Seed Marchant – 3; Tourism – 2.

In terms of delegates affiliations, 78% were from the UK, whilst 22% came from other European countries (Figure 2A.). Most of the participants were not partners of the RADIANT project (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. Description of the group of registered participants: (A) country of origin: United Kingdom – 40, Italy – 4, Ireland – 3, Portugal – 2, Netherlands – 1; (B) whether they are a partner of the RADIANT project (31) or not (20), and if they were present in-person (40) or online (10).

Day 1

The first day of the workshop was dedicated to showcase the genetic diversity of bere for breeders to tackle issues of agricultural sustainability and its heritage value of bere, as a source of novel high-value Scottish products. The day was divided into the following four sessions:

- short perspectives from a variety of bere-focused stakeholders;
- bere Showcase: heritage, sustainability, and commercialisation;
- workshop activities: parallel consultations & group discussions; and,
- bere product tasting event.

All participants were welcomed by Prof. Edward Abbott Halpin, Principal Orkney College at the University of the Highlands and Islands. Prof. Marta Vasconcelos then introduced the RADIANT project: 'Realizing Dynamic Value Chains for underutilised crops' followed by Dr Pietro (Pete) Iannetta, who presented the programme for the day (Annex 1). Peter Martin, Director of the University of the Highlands and Islands, Agronomy Institute, gave the last presentation of the session on 'Commercialising Orkney Bere'.

Participants were then given short perspectives from a variety of bere-focused stakeholders ranging from:

- an environmental archaeologist specialising in ancient crops (**Michael Wallace**) from the University of Sheffield and Headland Archaeology giving the audience its perspective on bere in the ancient past and how we might recognise the landrace in the archaeological record;
- a Barley geneticist (**Joanne Russell**) at the James Hutton Institute providing insights into the genetics of bere barley as a potential resource for the future;
- a Rhizosphere scientist (**Tim George**) at the James Hutton Institute sharing current knowledge of stress tolerance of bere; and,
- an independent food writer (**Elizabeth Ashworth**) gave a perspective of the historical use of bere in the recent past and the burgeoning interest in using bere as an ingredient in cooking and baking today.

For more details on the presentations, see section 2 (Presentations) below. These talks were followed by a short Q&A session before delegates were given the opportunity to visit the ongoing field trials at Orkney College (Figure 2). This included visits to the college fields and polytunnels where the Agronomy Institute grows bere commercially and in trials and does research into the growth of alternative and underutilised crops in Orkney including tea and a range of berries.

Figure 2. Visit of the University of the Highlands & Islands field trials.

Following lunch, the 'Bere showcase heritage, sustainability, and commercialisation' session was kicked-off by spotlight presentations given by:

- **Lesley McGeachy**, senior tour guide and distillery ambassador at Bruichladdich Distillery, which produces bere Barley whiskies;
- **Colin Johnston**, Craft Sales & Marketing Manager for Crisp Malt, which malt barley for distillers and brewers around the world; and,
- **Rachel Scarth**, Chair of Birsay Heritage Trust, which is responsible for the running of Barony mill and the growing, harvesting and milling of bere and oversee the wholesale and retail selling of beremeal.

Whilst the 2nd session of the day mainly focussed on bere cultivation both in history and in current days, this session aimed to showcase the processing and marketing to consumers of novel bere-based products as illustrations of successful realisation of dynamic value chains for this underutilised crop.

Participants were then divided into three groups to participate in parallel consultations and group discussions. In those groups, the following were discussed (for more details, see section 4.2. below):

- **Farmer’s consultation.** Producers were asked to complete the initial sections of questionnaire concerning the cultivation of bere. This was followed by a group discussion to explore barriers and drivers of underutilised crops on your farm, and then the final section of the questionnaire was completed.
- **Consumer’s consultation.** Consumers were asked to complete a questionnaire regarding their preferences regarding bere-based products. This was also followed by a group discussion to explore barriers and drivers of the consumption of underutilised crops.
- **All other delegates.** Perspectives were sought on factors which underpin the cultivation and consumption of underutilised crops. The discussion focussed mainly on the question of whether bere should seek Protected Designation of Origin status and what implications the Nagoya protocol has on the use of bere.

The last session of the day was the “Tasting event”, when participants were given the opportunity to taste a range of bere-based products including whiskies from [Bruichladdich Distillery](#), beers from [Swannay Brewery](#), and biscuits from [Barony Mill](#) (Figure 3 and Figure 4). This included a presentation and tasting notes of the latest whisky made from bere by Bruichladdich (bere barley 2012) along with tasting notes given by Lesley McGeachy. There was also an opportunity to interact with value chain stakeholder at demonstration stalls from Barony Mill with products and information, Orkney Museum with a working hand quern, and James Hutton Institute and SRUC with information about their participatory research approaches.

Figure 3. Photos of participants taking part in the whiskies tasting.

Figure 4. Examples of bere-based products showcased at the tasting event: beers from [Swannay Brewery](#), whiskies from [Bruichladdich Distillery](#), and biscuits and bread from [Barony Mill](#).

The first day of the event was concluded by an official dinner at [the Storehouse Restaurant](#) sponsored by the James Hutton Institute.

Day 2

Day 2 was dedicated to visits to some of the significant players in the bere value chain, which included:

- [Swannay Brewery](#), brewing beers with Orkney grown bere barley;
- [Barony Mill](#), Orkney's only working water mill, home of Orkney beremeal; and,
- Burray Field Visit, plot trials of bere vs. conventional barley.

Participants were also given the chance to visit [The Ness of Brodgar](#), one of the most important archaeological excavations in the world today. For more details on these visits, see [Section 3](#). below.

2. Presentations

2.1 Presentations Overview

Presentations can be found from the [Radiant bere Barley Event](#) webpage.

Introduction - to the RADIANT Project, Bere Barley and Orkney

Commercialisation of Bere Barley in Orkney

Peter Martin, University of the Highlands & Islands

Peter gave a presentation during the session on 'Commercializing Orkney Bere' which demonstrated the diverse range of value chains associated with bere and developed over the last 20 years.

Short perspectives from a variety of bere-focused stakeholders

Bere in the ancient past: how we might recognise the landrace in the archaeological record

Michael Wallace, University of Sheffield, and Headland Archaeology

Michael gave the audience its perspective on bere in the ancient past and how we might recognise the landrace in the archaeological record using modern morphometric techniques. His findings suggest that bere has been in Orkney for much longer than first thought, dating back to well before the Norse settlement (9th century AD).

Genetics of Bere

Joanne Russell, James Hutton Institute

With the yield of barley stagnating across Europe, researchers are returning to the importance of old cultivars and wild relatives as sources of beneficial

variation to ensure the future efficiency of agriculture under a changing climate and limited resources. Large seed collections are available globally for barley and we have focussed on old cultivars that have been collected from the UK, grown for a hundred years or so, surviving both changes in climate and agricultural practise. The collection known as 'heritage barleys' includes accessions from the 1800s from England, Ireland, Wales, and Scotland, many of which are the cornerstones of modern UK cultivars. These 140 accessions have been scored for yield, earliness, quality, and nutrient efficiency traits under field conditions over several years and compared to current elite lines to identify novel variation. To exploit this potentially useful variation we are using a targeted introgression programme in collaboration with UK barley breeders at KWS. This strategy emphasises the importance of connecting old cultivar collections (maintained by gene banks) to state-of-the-art gene discovery to phenotyping and ultimately targeted breeding approaches providing resources for our future needs.

Stress Tolerance of Bere

Timothy George, James Hutton Institute

Tim shared current knowledge of stress tolerance of bere, which showed that bere has a unique ability to cope with manganese deficient marginal soils found in Orkney and other parts of the world.

Bere Showcase: heritage, sustainability, and commercialisation

Spotlight presentations from bere-focused stakeholders.

Lesley McGeachy

Lesley gave a perspective on the important of bere to their whisky production in Islay.

Crisp Malt - *Colin Johnston*

Colin also discussed the relevance of bere as part of their supply chain.

Birsay Heritage Trust
Rachel Scarth

Rachel is responsible for the running of Barony mill and the growing, harvesting and milling of bere and oversee the wholesale and retail selling of beremeal.

3. Field visits

3.1. Ness of Brodgar

The Ness of Brodgar site is one of the most important archaeological excavations in the world today, changing our understanding of the culture and beliefs of Neolithic Orkney and shining a new light on the prehistory of northern Europe. The site has been under excavation since 2004, revealing a massive complex of monumental Neolithic buildings dating from the centuries around 3000 BC. Participants of the workshop were shown around some of the structures (structures 1 to 10) excavated to date and heard about their suggested uses based on artefacts recovered, animal bones excavated and shapes of the structures (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Photos of the Ness of Brodgar excavation sites.

3.2 Swannay Brewery

[Swannay Brewery](#) is a local brewery (Figure 6) located on the north-westerly tip of Orkney's mainland, a wind-battered area known as Swannay. Lewis Hill (son of the founder) described how the brewery was set up and how discussion with Peter Martin from the University of Highlands and Islands persuaded them to try to brew beers with bere barley. The collection now includes 3 beers brewed and canned locally in Orkney. Lewis also explained the impact of COVID-19 had on the brewery and its sales, which saw a huge increase in online sales during that period. The pandemic also allowed the brewery to progressively move from bottled beers, which is done on the mainland, to canned beers, which they can do on-site. They also reported an increased interests from locals seeking local produce.

Figure 6. Tour of Swannay Brewery.

3.3 Barony Mill

Barony Mill

[Barony Mill](#) is Orkney's only working water mill, home of Orkney beremeal since 1873. It is the main mill in the UK that deals with bere. It was explained to participants that the mill was built in 1873, and that little has changed in it since then. Like most northern mills of this period, a kiln for drying the grain is integrated with the building. Grinding is done in the winter; during summer, the Mill is open to the public. The miller described how the machinery works from hoisting the sacks of grain to the top of mill, drying the grain, and milling the grain using waterpower (Figure 7). The flour produced is called beremeal. Beremeal is available for sale for home use and for commercial bakers (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Photos of Barony Mill and bere-based products.

3.4 Burray Field Visit

Participants then visited the Burray field trials where plots of bere are grown alongside Rye, oats and modern Barley (Figure 8). These demonstrated how bere is better adapted to the north of Scotland’s climate, and the low nutrient soils of marginal lands (e.g., manganese on alkaline soils).

Figure 8. Photos of participants in the cereal trials at Orkney College (top) and Burray (bottom).

4. Outputs of discussions

4.1 Summary

Bere and bere products offer several unique selling points to growers and consumers including unique flavour, enhanced nutritional (e.g., protein) provision, cultural and heritage value, adaptations for growing on low-fertility soils and with low-input systems. The latter results in a lower environmental impact e.g., reduced Greenhouse Gas (GHG) footprint via lower synthetic nitrogen fertiliser use for production - though a bere specific Life Cycle Analyses remain to be undertaken (this may be done in the scope of the RADIANT project). However, yields are low, the crop is tall and subject to lodging and can be challenging to harvest, dry, and process. Additionally, bere-based products are expensive and feature as luxury items, and there is a trade-off here between ensuring bere remains exclusive to its original growing centres, and market expansion. Management of the value chain expansion with respect to preserving the bere heritage and genetic diversity, may be an opportunity for consultants experienced in the premiumisation of Scottish food and drink. There may be value using this workshop as a springboard to forming a bere multi-stakeholders group which meets regularly to develop and implement a 'bere strategic-action plan', which will safeguard and manage the use of the many varied bere genotypes, and develop stronger more resilient bere-based value chains.

4.2 Breakout sessions

During the workshop session, participants were divided into three groups to discuss specific topics as detailed below.

Group 1: Farmer's consultation.

Four farmers took part in a workshop on cultivation of bere which included a questionnaire about their attitudes and farm activities, a deliberative choice experiment, and a discussion of the barriers and drivers of growing bere.

All participants were male, older than 30, and came from different regions in Scotland. They own their agricultural land (three farms have less than 80 hectares and one has over 300 ha) and have been working as farmer for 28 years on average. Their crop production is mixed, although they specialise in cereals. The level of crop diversity in the farms is low as only one farmer reported growing more than three crops. None of the respondents is part of a farmers' group.

Three of the farmers had previous knowledge about the crop, as they were already growing bere Barley (on 9% of land on average). Nonetheless, during the discussion, they brought to our attention that farmers do not focus on the financial gain whilst growing this crop and instead, they do it as an experiment or subsistence/rotation crop. Farmers also declared that they currently struggle to perceive bere barley as a profitable crop, however, they agreed with its market potential. In regard to the profitability of bere barley, a farmer highlighted that even if consumers are willing to pay a premium price, farmers will only be likely to grow a new crop if the financial gain goes to them and not to the middleman. This suggests that **farmers prefer shorter market chains for underutilised crops.**

Farmers' perception of the adoption of new crops was mixed, but most stated that there are not many market opportunities to adopt new crops. The limited sample did not provide enough response variability and did not allow for identifying factors determining the adoption of new crops. Three out of four farmers disagreed with statements declaring that whilst adopting crops they preferred to grow crops with high resistance to pests, easy accessibility to seeds, low-risk returns, and crops which were not time-consuming and labour-intensive. Nonetheless, at least half of the farmers declared that they

would only adopt new crops if they had technical assistance. The latter finding **may indicate that farmers care about the provision of technical assistance when adopting new crops.**

The workshop also provided us with helpful feedback on our survey instrument. Overall, farmers thought the survey was clear, had a logical order and had accessible language. They also thought the introductory text was clear and agreed with the information presented on “the benefits of growing bere barley”. However, it was suggested to add more detailed information on the practical relevance of this survey by carefully explaining how we will use the information collected.

The feedback regarding the main part of the survey, the discrete choice experiment, was positive. Farmers thought that the choice cards used in the questionnaire were clear. They liked the images and understood how to answer them. They considered that the card combinations made sense but mentioned that it took them some time to devise how the attribute combinations would adapt to their farms.

Farmers thought all the attributes used in the choice cards were clear and important. They reacted to the price attributes as expected; that is, they considered that the top price attribute level was too high, and the first two bottom levels were too low. A larger sample size is needed to develop a robust test on the price attribute levels. However, it is important to note that one farmer commented that he ignored the cost attribute as he is not growing bere barley for financial gains.

In general, farmers understood the “informal risk sharing” attribute. For example, a farmer mentioned that currently, there is a similar initiative to share risks amongst farmers belonging to a cooperative growing peas, in which it is agreed that all members will get paid regardless of their yield outcomes. Nonetheless, they also highlighted that this kind of risk-sharing

mechanism is not “informal” and would only work on a local or regional scale. Regarding the omission of important attributes, a few farmers noted that it would be essential to consider an attribute related to the existence of the necessary infrastructure needed to process the crop (e.g., small-scale malting equipment).

The feedback from the workshop also permitted us to identify issues with our survey instrument. Overall, farmers considered that the survey was too long. It was suggested that answering eight choice cards was tiring; thus, future designs with fewer cards and more blocks can be explored.

After filling out the questionnaire, farmers participated on a SWOT analysis to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats with respect to the goal of expanding the bere supply chain. The survey was filled on tablets, while the results from the SWOT analysis were written on large paper sheets.

The SWOT analysis highlighted the following elements:

- **Strengths:** increase diversity of crops; less vulnerable to climate change; and less affected by diseases; more resilient; special flavour; local crop (local origin or provenance; premium price; can generate own seed; health benefits (e.g., less gluten and high nutrients); multiple yield.
- **Weaknesses:** missing infrastructure; lack of knowledge to grow it; low yield; limited access to seed; soil quality.
- **Opportunities:** new market opportunity; niche market; gap in the market (e.g., cosmetic use); existing group of stakeholders providing support and promoting the use of bere; can be grown in marginal soil; generation of policies that promote crop diversity; promotes the consumption of local crops/food.
- **Threats:** infrastructure hold by few agents; lack of support leading to unsuccessful yields; climate global changes; restrictive policies.

Figure 9. Attributes used in the choice experiments with farmers (left) and consumers (right).

Group 2: Consumer’s consultation.

Eleven consumers took part in a workshop on the consumption of bere-based products, which included a questionnaire with a pilot choice experiment, and a discussion to explore barriers and drivers of the consumption of underutilised crops.

Seven of the eleven participants were females, four were males. A plurality (four) was 65–75 year-old, two each 35-44, 45-54 and 55-64 year old, and one, over 75. Five of them had children in their household. Their average level of education was high, with five having college education and six postgraduates, and their monthly household income ranged from less than £1,200 to more than £5,200 a month, with half earning less than £2,000. Five came from the Orkney islands, two from the Highlands, two from the rest of Scotland, and two from England.

Ten were “exclusively” or “mostly” responsible for shopping for food in their household, and eight “exclusively” or “mostly” responsible for cooking, which ensures that their responses are representative of their household’s food behaviours. All of them considered the healthiness and diversity of diets “somewhat” or “very important”, and indeed had a “somewhat” or “very diverse” diet. A majority (seven) shops mainly in supermarkets (which were the second option for the others), and two in each local markets and independent shops.

Overall, the participants appreciated the importance of crop and genetic diversity for several reasons and considered it important to take action for this purpose; but they also thought that people in their community were not equally concerned. They also had a positive consideration for local crops, underutilised crops, and derived food products; but they agreed that it is difficult to find places where to purchase them.

All but one participant knew about bere before attending the workshop, and all but two had consumed bere products. Regardless of bere, eight of them consumed flour few times per week, while only seven of them purchased beer more than once a month, and only four consumed whiskies once a month or more often.

Therefore, the sample was not representative of the population of Scottish consumers: they were older and more educated than average; they were aware food consumers; they were concerned about genetic and crop diversity and about underutilised crops; and they came mostly from the Orkney islands. This implies that the results of the discussion cannot be extended to the overall population. However, given their knowledge of bere, their reflections in this regard are highly valuable.

The consumers filled a questionnaire, including a choice experiment. This was followed by a discussion of the content of the choice cards, and by a SWOT

analysis to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunity, and threats with respect to the goal of expanding the bere supply chain. The survey was filled on tablets, while the SWOT analysis was implemented using sticky notes on a whiteboard.

The length of the questionnaire was judged adequate, but some of the consumers stated that they had not really understood how to answer the choice cards and wanted to come back to previous choices to check if their responses were coherent along the questionnaire. A relevant challenge in this regard was that the choice questionnaire did not specify the use of the flour purchased; indeed, the choice would change depending on the use (bread, oatcakes, biscuits, *etc.*), since the flours are not perfect substitutes. The participants that were used to cooking with bere flour felt that the cards were written by someone who did not really understand how beremeal is used (which is indeed the case). In the future, it was suggested to specify the use, or focus the cards on the final product (*e.g.*, oatcakes) rather than the flour itself. The consumers were told to answer all the cards with respect to the same potential use of the flour. The "origin" attribute was somehow problematic because "local" was not nested into "Scotland" for those coming from England. The prices were judged somewhat extreme, and too variable considering that the differences between the products proposed were limited. The fact that the flour is stone ground emerged as a potential additional attribute of relevance (for example, a local Orkney mill uses stones to produce bere flour). The respondents also felt that more details about what bere is, and its story, should be provided at the start of the survey.

The consumers argued that the crop should be called "bere" rather than "bere barley", as it is a different crop; for example, someone calls it "corn". Equally, "underutilised crop" sounds like a very scientific term and does not really grab consumers' attention. "Artisan crop" or "heritage crop" would be better, while "local" captures only one dimension. "Landraces" is another option but not very used by lay consumers. In general, knowledge of this crop is limited

among consumers outside the Orkney islands and Scotland; therefore, its specificity is a double-edged sword. Education of the youth and of consumers in general is key, not only for what concerns bere but also on food management and the importance of crop and dietary diversity. A potential strategy to increase the diffusion of bere is to convince bakeries to use the flour, and then make the bere content clear in the label. However, until investors are willing to invest into the development of beremeal as a flour, this will remain a niche market. There have been attempts in the past at developing bere products, but no one has developed these ideas further; indeed, the big economic players are happy with the *status quo*. Standard consumers are very unlikely to be able to say if, *e.g.*, a biscuit contains beremeal.

Currently, there is a huge difference between the proportions of bere grown for malting and for flour (80% to 20%). On the one hand, many small brewers would be keen to get bere malt, but there are no specific facilities for making malt at commercial scales/qualities, and this is a labour-intensive process. On the other hand, the need for flour is less likely to be affected by economic downturns like the current one, because people will always need bread; small-scale distilleries and brewers are more likely to disappear in case of recession if the large amount of the population does not have the spare cash to spend on alcohol.

The characteristics of bere flour and its uses were extensively discussed. Bere flour is not comparable to the other flours considered in the choice experiment (maize and wheat), and is usually mixed with them (*e.g.*, a little of beremeal and more wheat flour); therefore, they should not be provided as a comparison. The mix and the suitability of bere flour also depend on the final product; therefore, the decision on whether to purchase it depends on what people are supposed to do with it. The need to mix it with other flours implies that bere flour cannot become mainstream and cannot replace more widespread flours but needs to accompany them; however, the use of local

wheat and maize varieties could ensure that other underutilised crops are used jointly.

Besides the use of bere fours by consumers in the UK, bere is important for Orkney for all what comes around it (whisky, beer, berries, *etc.*, as well as innovations such as using it in the tea). From this point of view, it can become a selling point for the territory and its uniqueness.

The **SWOT** analysis highlighted the following elements.

- **Strengths:** the flavour of bere products; the heritage and history as a unique selling point (although there is only limited knowledge outside Orkney and Scotland; furthermore, someone argued that not many consumers care about history); low gluten levels (although it is still not suitable for all celiac people); suitability for poor soils where other varieties cannot be grown, and for harsh weather conditions.
- **Weaknesses:** the yield, because it is low; the difficulty in mechanising farm processes; the need of adding a raising agent to the flour for making bread and other products; the limited knowledge of bere and of its uniqueness outside Orkney and Scotland; the limited suitability for rich soils; the need to dry the grains to take them to 14% moisture, which is an expensive process.
- **Opportunities:** the low carbon footprint, which makes it desirable in the perspective of fighting climate change; the heritage and history as a unique selling point (if knowledge is spread further).
- **Threats:** the large markup introduced by retailers prevents bere from becoming mainstream, especially among consumers with a tiny budget and in high inflation times; the loss of payments for farmers growing bere, which makes it profitable only if they can get a higher selling price; the high investments needed; climate change (which implies drier season, and more extreme events); the fact that specificity can be lost if the supply chain expands.

Figure 10. Flipcharts with the sticky notes from the SWOT analysis with consumers.

To conclude, a key point that emerged from the discussion was the trade-off between expanding / mainstreaming the bere supply chain, which entails the risk of losing local specificity as a “unique selling point”; and maintaining it as a niche product which attracts a higher price but only concerns a small segment of consumers. As long as beremeal is an artisanal product with additional premium, the people with more malnutrition and food security problems, which also have narrower budgets, would not be able to access it, which clearly underlined the current issues faced by transitioning to underutilised crops.

Group 3: All other delegates.

The discussion focussed mainly on whether it would be a good idea to get a Protected

Designation of Origin status for bere. There was a mixed reaction to this. Some thought the

status had potential for individual bere products and not for the grain itself due to potential issues ascertaining historical provenance (*i.e.*, Shetland bere, Western Isles bere, Orkney bere, Northern English bere *etc.*), while others considered it would limit production and global benefits available to growing bere. Interestingly, for some of the value chain stakeholders, there was little interest in expanding production beyond current output as they do not have the capacity. So, PDO status for the manufacturing process of bere-based products (*e.g.*, beremeal) could be advantageous as Orkney beremeal is different from other beremeal. Hence, the PDO could increase the value of the product, making small scale production more profitable.

Extending the theme of protecting- and adding-value to bere, the discussion also highlighted the need for more local maltings of bere to allow greater local diversification of products. There seems to be a great need for a maltings in Orkney and the potential of small-scale malting on-farm was also discussed to further reduce the environmental impacts of local beverages.

Interestingly, avenues for collaborations between RADIANT partners and bere value chain stakeholders were explored to help stakeholders grow the value chain. Ideas suggested included:

- full Life-Cycle Analysis (LCA) of the value chain to quantify the value of bere, which will include a calculation of ecosystem services, social aspects and affected biodiversity;
- LCA of bere production vs. conventional barley production;
- nutritional analysis of a bere meal vs. a barley meal to help with health promotion benefits of bere and improve marketing; and,
- translation of available bere-based recipes.

5. Concluding remarks

The main points and lessons learned during the workshop are the following. The two existing bere value chains in Orkney, are commercially well-developed compared to bere value chains operating in the Western Isles (the other main location of bere production) where it is, currently, mainly used on-farm as one component of a cereal landrace mix used for animal feed. Nevertheless, the maintenance of the value chains appeared precarious, and dependent upon the UHI Agronomy Institute and Birsay Heritage Trust, working with separate contractors. Collectively, the Institute, Trust and their contractors have the expertise and capacities to grow bere consistently across various farms. The grain is dried separately by each value chain before distribution either as seed for re-sowing, milling by Barony Mill, or malting on the mainland.

The situation with bere on Orkney is very different to that on the Western Isles where bere is currently mainly grown as one component of a landrace crop mixture (bere, black oats and rye) which is used for animal feed over the winter. The only mono crop fields of bere on the Western Isles are those which are grown for seed and a serious threat to these fields comes from geese and deer. A number of stakeholders on the Western Isles are aware of the potential for growing bere for malting and local alcohol production and preliminary trials are starting to investigate this. In both the Western Isles and Orkney, therefore, seed is produced by a relatively small number of growers which raises questions regarding the extent to which the types cultivated really reflect what would have been locally adapted genotypes or landraces. Taken together, the bere value chains in Orkney and the Western Isles are therefore precarious. Diversification of this base, whilst ensuring the maintenance of bere functional and genetic diversity, would demand the development of more short-value chains, such development would in-turn demand investment of local processing facilities, including the capacities of on-farm processing to human good grades. Equally, there remains the concern that the unique heritage characteristics and local-cultural values

offered by bere may be forfeited if the market is expanded. Whichever route is used to maintain and consolidate the market for bere, the germplasm collection held by JHI is also of critical importance to protect and/or diversify the bere value chains, and with respect to the original genotypes grown in each Scottish region.

To conclude, safeguarding the future of bere will require concerted action, and most likely a 'strategic action plan' with possible linked funding support from regional and national government agencies, plus linked local development agencies (such as Scottish Enterprise). Towards this end, 2023 will mark the 150th anniversary of Barony Mill, and a bere Celebration workshop is planned. This requires support, and workshop participants discussed the possibility of seeking support through the [SEFARI Gateway](#) funding. In addition, this workshop would also be used as the first 'bere symposium' and foundation from which bere-focused stakeholders may be drawn together on a more regular basis, and with a view to generating the 'bere strategic-action plan' alluded to above.

Annex I - Program

RADIANT CREATOR Workshop – Bere Programme

**Day 1: July 11th, 2022
Workshop, Orkney College**

09:30 Registration

Introduction - to the RADIANT Project, Bere Barley and Orkney

10:00 **Welcome to the College and Orkney**
Edward Abbott Halpin, University of the Highlands & Islands

10:10 **Introduction to the RADIANT Project & CREATOR workshop**
Marta Vasconcelos, Catholic University of Porto
Pietro (Pete) Iannetta, James Hutton Institute

10:25 **Commercialisation of Bere Barley in Orkney**
Peter Martin, University of the Highlands & Islands

Short perspectives from a variety of Bere-focused stakeholders

10:40 **Bere in the ancient past: how we might recognise the landrace in the archaeological record**
Michael Wallace, University of Sheffield and Headland Archaeology

10:55 **Genetics of Bere**
Joanne Russell, James Hutton Institute

11:05 **Stress Tolerance of Bere**
Timothy George, James Hutton Institute

11:15 **Bere and brewing history**
Susan Flavin, Trinity College Dublin

11:30 Panel & Delegates Discussion

12:00 Lunch (with optional field trial visit at 12:30)

Bere Showcase: heritage, sustainability, and commercialisation

13:00 Free time to visit the stalls. Spotlight presentations will be given:

- **13:15 Bruichladdich Distillery** - Lesley McGeachy
- **13:45 Crisp Malt** - Colin Johnston
- **14:00 Birsay Heritage Trust** – Rachel Scarth

14:15 Coffee Break

Workshop activities: parallel consultations & group discussions

14:30 Delegates divided into 3 groups to discuss the following:

Workshop 1: Farmer’s consultation (Blue Group). Producers will be asked to complete the initial sections of questionnaire concerning the cultivation of Bere. This will be followed by a group discussion to explore barriers and drivers of underutilised crops on your farm, and then the final section of the questionnaire will be completed.

Workshop 2: Consumer’s consultation (Red/Orange Group). Consumers will be asked to complete a questionnaire regarding their preferences regarding Bere-based products. This will be followed by a group discussion to explore barriers and drivers of the consumption of underutilised crops.

Workshop 3: All other delegates (Green and Yellow Group). Perspectives will be sought on factors which underpin the cultivation and consumption of underutilised crops. The discussion should also consider what it means to have a ‘dynamic value chain’ for underutilised crops.

17:00 Bere product tasting event

19:30 Dinner at the Storehouse, Kirkwall
thestorehouserestaurantwithrooms.co.uk

Day 2: July 12th, 2022
Field Trial Visits, Orkney History Talk on the bus

- 08:30** **Pick up at Orkney college**
- 09:00 Ness of Brodgar Visit
- 10:30 Swannay Brewery (<https://www.swannaybrewery.com/>)
- 11:30 Barony Mill (<https://baronymill.com/visit/>)
- 12:30** **Lunch - Birsay Community Hall** (<http://www.birsayhall.co.uk/>)
- 13:30** **Coach Departure**
- 14:30 Burray Field Visit
- Including airport drop offs at 14:00 and 16:30.
- 17:00** **Return to Orkney college**

